

Physicochemical Studies of 3d-Metal Complexes of Potassium Ethylene Dixanthate

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Interaction of some 3d-metals with potassium ethylene dixanthate has been extensively studied by different physicochemical methods. Electrometric and chemical analysis gave 1 : 1 metal-ligand ratio. All the complexes are found to be paramagnetic showing magnetic moment values corresponding to the spin values of unpaired electrons. All the xanthato complexes are high-spin, having octahedral stereochemistry with sp^3d^2 hybridisation except Cu-complex which has square-planar geometry with dsp^2 hybridisation. Infrared spectral data showed M-S bonding and coordinated water in all the complexes except copper complex where water is present as a water of crystallisation.

IN continuation to our earlier work¹ on the complexing behaviour of potassium ethylene hydroxy xanthate (PEHX), we report herein the results on the stoichiometric and structural studies of 3d-metal complexes of potassium ethylene dixanthate.

Experimental

Potassium ethylene dixanthate (abbreviated hereafter as PEDX) was prepared by the method of Dautzenberg² with some improvement as : 1 M ethylene glycol was strongly refluxed with 2.5 M KOH above 163° for 2-3 h. Clear solution was decanted when hot, cooled and to it 2.2 M CS_2 was added dropwise (in 1 h) with vigorous stirring followed by the addition of 1 M dimethyl sulphoxide. Contents were further stirred until the product was separated. It was filtered, washed with ether and recrystallised (75% yield) and analysed for sulphur (Found : 43.20. Calcd. for 44.17%). The compound was characterised by ir spectroscopy.

Fresh solution of the ligand was always used. Stock solutions of manganese chloride, ferric chloride, cobaltous chloride, nickel sulphate and cupric acetate were prepared in double-distilled water. Fresh solution of ferrous sulphate was always used. The strength of these solutions was determined by the usual methods. All the chemicals used were of analytical grade.

Conductometric titrations of the ligand against metals were carried out according to monovariation method at room temperature to determine the

stoichiometry of the complexes. A Toshniwal 0102A conductivity bridge with dip type conductivity cell was used throughout the measurement. Amperometric titrations (both direct and reverse) were performed using 0.02 M solutions of metals and ligand in presence of 0.2 M KCl as supporting electrolyte and 0.1% solution of gelatin as maximum-suppressor (N_2 gas was used for deaeration as well as for stirring the solution). The observed diffusion current was corrected for dilutions and plotted against the volume of metal (or ligand) to give M-L ratio.

Complexes were isolated by mixing equimolecular solutions of metal salt and the ligand in 1 : 1 M-L ratio. Resulting compounds were filtered, purified with methanol, dried in vacuum desiccator and analysed for metal and sulphur to establish the empirical formula of the complexes (Table 1).

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
	Metal	S	Cl
$C_4H_6O_4S_4Mn$	17.81 (18.11)	43.51 (42.29)	—
$C_4H_6O_4S_4Fe$	17.65 (18.36)	43.62 (42.16)	—
$C_4H_6O_4S_4FeCl$	17.68 (17.36)	40.58 (39.87)	11.42 (11.02)
$C_4H_6O_4S_4Co$	18.85 (19.18)	41.02 (41.74)	—
$C_4H_6O_4S_4Ni$	18.86 (19.12)	42.55 (41.77)	—
$C_4H_6O_4S_4Cu$	20.68 (20.37)	40.88 (41.12)	—

TABLE 2—MAGNETIC DATA OF COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd *	K	Corrected molar susceptibility χ_M (c. g. s. units)	μ_{eff} (B. M.)			No. of unpaired elec.rons
				Found	Calcd.	Reported	
1.	$C_4H_8O_4S_4Mn$	300	1.488×10^{-5}	5.98	5.92	5.65–6.10	5
2.	$C_4H_8O_4S_4Fe$	300	1.041×10^{-5}	5.00	4.90	4.80–5.60	4
3.	$C_4H_8O_4S_4FeCl$	300	1.449×10^{-5}	5.90	5.92	5.70–6.05	5
4.	$C_4H_8O_4S_4Co$	300	6.494×10^{-6}	3.95	3.88	4.30–5.20	3
5.	$C_4H_8O_4S_4Ni$	300	3.991×10^{-6}	3.10	2.83	2.80–3.50	2
6.	$C_4H_8O_4S_4Cu$	300	1.503×10^{-6}	1.90	1.70	1.71–2.20	1

*All compounds have high-spin octahedral sp^3d^2 , except Sl. no. 6 which has square-planar dsp^2 hybridisation.

The magnetic susceptibilities of the complexes were recorded at 30° on a Meltov Zoric type Gouy's magnetic balance and corrected for diamagnetic contributions. Values of corrected molar susceptibilities χ_M' and magnetic moment, μ_{eff} are given in Table 2. Infrared spectra of the ligand and the complexes were recorded in KBr medium on a Beckman IR 20 spectrophotometer to decide the bonding sites and to establish the structure of the complexes.

Results and Discussion

Preliminary investigations revealed that metal salt solutions of Mn^{II} , Fe^{II} , Fe^{III} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} when mixed with aqueous solution of PEDX yielded light yellow, brown, dark brown, dull green, greenish yellow and brownish yellow precipitate, respectively. Direct and reverse electro-metric titration curves were found to be conventional, breaking at 1:1 metal–ligand ratio in all the cases. Chemical analysis (Table 1), also supported the same stoichiometry.

The results of magnetic measurements (Table 2) were interpreted to explain the stereochemistry of the complexes. All the complexes were found to be paramagnetic with the magnetic moment values of 5.98, 5.0, 5.9, 3.95, 3.1 B.M. for Mn^{II} , Fe^{II} , Fe^{III} , Co^{II} and Ni^{II} , respectively. These values are in close agreement with the reported values for high-spin octahedral complexes involving sp^3d^2 hybridisation. The Cu^{II} complex was also found to be paramagnetic with magnetic

moment value of 1.9 B.M.; close to the reported values for square-planar complexes of Cu^{II} involving ds^2 hybridisation.

In the ir spectra of PEDX, bands at 1370, 990, 825 and 690 cm^{-1} were assigned for C:S stretching frequencies. Similar assignments³⁻⁵ have been made in thiosemicarbazides, thioacetamides and xanthates. In the ir spectra of ethylene dioxanthato complexes, these vibrations either disappeared or appeared in the lower frequency region (Table 3). Lowering or disappearance of C:S stretching vibrations is a strong evidence for the involvement of sulphur in the complexation. In the ir spectra of xanthato complexes, the appearance of new broad bands at 3380–3480 cm^{-1} and a sharp broad band at 1600–1620 cm^{-1} were suggested for ν_{OH} of the water. Broadness of these bands clearly indicated the presence of coordinated water. Furthermore, the presence of coordinated water in all these complexes (except Cu-complex) was confirmed by the fact that loss in weight was not significant and thus ruled out the possibilities of lattice water, though the spectra of the complexes showed no tracing of a absorption band at 3680–3700 cm^{-1} as shown by the anti-symmetric and symmetric stretching modes of the coordinated water⁶. No reason of this missing band is clear. But in the case of the copper complex, the observed weight loss, corresponded closely to two moles of water, proving its presence as lattice water in the complex. Sharp bands at 1120 and 1210 cm^{-1} in the ir spectra of PEDX were

TABLE 3—INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA AND THEIR TENTATIVE ASSIGNMENTS

PEDX	Mn^{II} complex	Fe^{II} complex	Fe^{III} complex	Co^{II} complex	Ni^{II} complex	Cu^{II} complex	Assignment
–	3400–3480sb	3420–3480sb	3400–3480sb	3400–3480sb	3380–3480sb	3400–3480sb	ν_{OH} of attached water
–	1620sb	1630sb	1630s	1620sb	1600–1640sb	1620–1640sb	
1370s	1340s	d	d	d	d	d	$\nu_{C:S}$ (S involved)
1210m	1210m	1220m	1230m	1230m	1225m	1220m	ν_{C-O-C} (oxygen not involved)
1120s	1180s	1140s	1130s	1180s	1120–1140sb	1130s	
990s	860s	965s	960s	980sb	830m	d	ν_{C-S} (sulphur involved)
825s	720s	765s	760m	820m	775m	775m	
690s	d	620s	600sb	d	640sb	680sb	

s = Sharp, sb = sharp broad, sh = shoulder, m = medium, d = disappear.

assigned for C—O—C stretching vibrations according to Little *et al.*⁷. These vibrations in xanthato complexes appeared either at the same frequency or shifted to higher frequency region, suggesting that oxygen of C—O—C was not involved in complex formation. New medium absorption

band at 295 cm⁻¹ in the ir spectra of Fe^{III} complex was assigned to Fe—Cl. However, clean cut assignments of M—S and M—O were not possible because of their weak absorptions. On the basis of the above findings, following tentative structures may be proposed for these complexes.

M = Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}

Square-planar

Octahedral

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